

How agricultural subsidies shape local employment: Evidence from the French support policies for mountain areas.

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Abstract

Do place-based farm subsidies reshape rural labour markets beyond agriculture? We estimate the causal impact of France's Less Favoured Areas (LFA) on municipal employment over 1962–1990. Combining entropy balancing with staggered difference-in-differences on 23,685 municipalities, we differentiate the effects on salaried versus self-employed farm labour and also estimate geographic spillovers and sectoral multipliers. LFA municipalities gain about 10% salaried agricultural jobs but lose roughly 18% self-employment as farms merge and expand. Positive spillovers extend to neighbouring municipalities, treated or not, and multipliers occur in non-farm sectors: industry, trade, and services grow around subsidised areas, while agri-food and construction rise inside them. Treatment heterogeneity shows stronger gains where farms are mid-sized and close to urban centers. By revealing job-creating but composition-shifting and geographical and sectoral outward-spreading effects, our study highlights that a policy designed to offset natural handicaps also reconfigures local labour markets and local linkages.

JEL Classification: C21, Q18, R12

Keywords: Rural employment, Spillovers, Entropy Balancing, Less Favoured Areas.

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Highlights

- We assess French LFA's impact on farm jobs, spillovers, and sectoral multipliers.
- We use Entropy balancing with staggered DiD on 23,685 municipalities.
- LFA raises 10% salaried jobs, cuts 18% self-employment.
- Positive spillovers boost non-farm sectors within 15 km.
- Subsidies reshape labour markets beyond initial objectives.

1 Introduction

Agricultural employment has declined in every advanced economy. In France, it fell from 26% of total jobs in 1954 to under 3% in 2020, while the number of farms declined from 1.6 million (1970) to about 390 000 (2020). Mechanisation, rising productivity and greater specialisation accelerated concentration: the average farm size tripled from 20 ha in 1970 to more than 60 ha in 2020. National averages, however, mask sharp territorial contrasts. In mountain areas, topography and climate raise production costs; yet, farming remains essential for local employment and in limiting depopulation. These areas accounted for roughly 16% of French agricultural labour in the 1990s. Their share has fallen since then, but they still sustain regional labour markets where intensive farming is unviable. To mitigate such disadvantages, the European Union’s Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) created the Less Favoured Areas (LFA) in 1975. In the late 1950’s and early 1960’s, several countries, such as Switzerland, Austria, Italy and France, introduced comparable schemes. Framed as a rural development instrument, the LFA is allocated on the basis of the municipality in which the farm is located and pursues two goals: preventing rural exodus and sustaining farming in difficult areas.

Indeed, theoretically, subsidies can stabilise farm income and food supply [Gardner, 1992, Van Tongeren, 2008], reduce uncertainty, and allow farms to survive adverse shocks, thereby limiting out-migration [Lipton, 1977]. Higher real incomes may also trigger “induced innovation” [Hicks, 1932], encouraging labour-saving technologies and further mechanisation. Yet, empirical evidence is mixed. Some studies report positive employment effects of CAP payments [Olper et al., 2014, Garrone et al., 2019, Gallic and Marcus, 2019], mainly by narrowing wage gaps with non-farm sectors and deterring workers from leaving agriculture. Subsidies also mitigate land abandonment [Ito et al., 2019, Takayama et al., 2020, 2021]. Others find negative or insignificant impacts, varying with program design, context and employment type [Kaditi, 2013, Petrick and Zier, 2012, Dupraz and Latruffe, 2015, Bojnec and Fertő, 2022].

Careful evaluation of these policies is complex due to sectoral multipliers and geographical spillovers. On the one hand, agricultural policy may affect non-farm sectors. Historically, farm growth has financed industrialisation, raised demand for manufactures and stimulated overall development [Crafts, 1985, Bustos et al., 2016, 2020]. Two channels are at work. The demand channel states that higher farm productivity boosts rural income and demand for industrial goods, reallocating labour toward industry [Kongsamut et al., 2001, Gollin et al., 2002]. The supply channel suggests that if farm productivity rises faster than industrial productivity and both goods are complements, labour will migrate to industry [Ngai and Pissarides, 2007]. Open-economy models temper these mechanisms: imports, credit constraints or labour-market frictions may dilute subsidy effects [Matsuyama, 1992, Banerjee and Newman, 1993]. Moreover, structural change tends to reduce agricultural employment, even under generous support [Anderson et al., 2013, Christiaensen et al., 2021]. As these subsidies distort markets and may delay necessary reallocations, they have been heavily criticized.

On the other hand, as the LFA is a place-based policy, possible spatial general equilibrium effects [Krugman, 1991, Kline and Moretti, 2014] can amplify or reverse its direct objectives.

Labour mobility and intersectoral linkages can transmit policy shocks to neighbouring areas and/or to other sectors, producing indirect, and sometimes unintended, effects. Ignoring spatial interference among units may bias impact estimates [Roth et al., 2023]. In a context closely related to our study, Moretti [2010] shows that each additional job created by a place-based intervention can induce up to 0.3 non-farm jobs locally, with a strong spatial decay of such effects.

In this context, our paper evaluates the *total* impact of the LFA, on both direct municipal agricultural employment and broader multiplier effects on other sectors and geographic spillovers on neighboring municipalities. Indeed, existing work faces three limitations. First, agricultural employment is seldom disaggregated between salaried and self-employed workers; yet mechanisation may displace family labour while raising demand for hired skills [Alexiadis et al., 2013, Gallardo and Sauer, 2018]. Second, standard Difference-in-Differences (DiD) designs struggle with endogenous targeting as mountain municipalities differ systematically from the rest. Third, few studies analyse dynamic impacts, sectoral multipliers, or spatial spillovers.

To address these gaps, we analyze the dynamic impact of the LFA on disaggregated municipal-level agricultural employment (salaried *vs.* self-employed) in France from 1962 onward. We also assess spillover effects on neighboring municipalities and multiplier effects on non-agricultural sectors. Accordingly, this paper contributes to the evaluation of LFA effects by combining four methodological advances within a single empirical framework. First, it traces treatment over a long municipal panel (1962–1990), enabling us to compare short-lived with persistent impacts and to add to earlier evidence on land-use shifts and rural migration [Gallic and Marcus, 2019, Védrine, 2019]. Second, disaggregating agricultural employment reveals heterogeneous responses often obscured in past work [Kaditi, 2013, Dupraz and Latruffe, 2015, Bojnec and Fertó, 2022]. Third, by embedding spatial lags, the analysis relaxes the Stable Unit Treatment Value Assumption and captures geographic spillovers that can bias conventional estimates and have rarely been quantified in the CAP context [Blomquist and Nordin, 2017, Hornbeck and Keskin, 2015, Roth et al., 2023]. Finally, causal identification rests on Entropy Balancing [Hainmueller, 2012], a weighting scheme that achieves higher covariate balance relative to traditional matching or Difference-in-Differences designs and has proven effective in related policy evaluations [Neuenkirch and Neumeier, 2016].

We match population censuses, agricultural censuses and LFA registers at the municipal level, identifying treatment from the program’s start. For the period 1962–1990, we use Entropy Balancing as our main identification strategy, supplemented with staggered Difference-in-Differences and Entropy-DID for robustness. We find that LFA payments raise salaried farm employment but reduce self-employment, consistent with farm enlargement and substitution of family by hired labour. Effects emerge soon after 1975 and persist. Impacts are strongest among mid-sized farms. We also find significant transmission to neighbouring municipalities, treated or not, and to non-farm sectors. This shift from family to salaried employment, along with significant spillovers to neighbouring municipalities and non-farm sectors, are unintended from the original policy rationale, aimed at preserving farming activity in disadvantaged mountain areas.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature studying the agricultural policies' impact on rural employment, and Section 3 describes the LFA program. Data and sample are presented in Section 4, followed by the presentation of our empirical strategy in Section 5. Section 6 presents our main results. Finally, Section 7 discusses the results, and Section 8 concludes.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Impact of Agricultural Policies on Agricultural Employment

Empirical research on how subsidies shape farm labour offers contrasting conclusions. Several multi-country analyses report positive employment effects when support raises farm income or funds training and capital formation. Examining 150 EU regions, [Olper et al. \[2014\]](#) shows that first-pillar payments stabilise agricultural jobs, roughly twice as effectively as rural development measures, while decoupled payments slow labour outflow across Europe [[Gallic and Marcus, 2019](#)]. At finer scales, funding allocated under rural development programs is positively correlated with job creation [[Angioloni et al., 2019](#)].

However, other studies suggest that subsidies can accelerate labour decrease by encouraging mechanisation or size enlargement. In East Germany, investment aid failed to mitigate employment losses and, in some cases, even exacerbated job destruction [[Petrick and Zier, 2011](#)]. Similar patterns emerge where CAP has favoured capital-intensive technologies [[Edan et al., 2009](#), [Gallardo and Sauer, 2018](#)]. Impacts also differ by worker type and instrument. In Greece, CAP reforms reduced family labour while boosting salaried employment, indicating substitution between the two categories [[Kaditi, 2013](#)]. France shows a comparable contrast: area-based and single-farm payments depress overall labour demand, whereas agri-environmental measures, disadvantaged-area (LFA) aid and investment grants raise employment, with salaried and family labour acting as complements [[Dupraz and Latruffe, 2015](#)]. Country contrasts are likewise evident in Hungary and Slovenia, where first-pillar transfers mainly support salaried labour in the former but family labour in the latter [[Bojnec and Fertó, 2022](#)].

From a cost-effectiveness perspective, targeted schemes can yield high returns. Swedish grassland support generated roughly 0.4 jobs per unit at a cost below the average wage [[Nordin, 2014](#)]. Conversely, removing export subsidies in Canada sharply decreased farm income and rural employment [[Bollman and Ferguson, 2019](#)]. Overall, the direction and magnitude of employment responses depend on the mix of instruments, local production structures, and the relative ease of substitution between capital and labour.

2.2 Spillover and Multiplier Effects of Agricultural Policies

Beyond farms, subsidies may spill over through local supply chains and labour markets. In Sweden, grassland transfers not only supported on-farm jobs but also raised private-sector employment more broadly [[Blomquist and Nordin, 2017](#)]. Conversely, the abolition of Canadian grain-export support eroded non-farm rural jobs, underscoring negative multipliers when farm

income contracts [Bollman and Ferguson, 2019]. Evidence from the United States is mixed: large groundwater windfalls boosted agricultural output yet delivered only transitory non-farm gains [Hornbeck and Keskin, 2015], whereas estimates of general public spending place the local income multiplier between 1.7 and 2, with the strongest effects in low-growth regions [Serrato and Wingender, 2016].

Empirical evidence on spatial spillovers is mixed. Using U.S. county data, Serrato and Wingender [2016] detect small spillovers across borders, suggesting that fiscal stimuli remain largely localised. By contrast, Auerbach et al. [2019] identify positive inter-jurisdictional spillovers that decay with distance, highlighting the need to model spatial linkages explicitly. These divergent findings imply that geographic proximity, sectoral composition, and labour mobility strongly condition whether subsidy benefits stay confined to treated areas or diffuse more widely.

Taken together, the literature indicates that CAP-type transfers can both create and destroy farm jobs, generate significant non-farm multipliers and, under certain conditions, spill over into neighbouring territories. The balance of these effects depends on policy design, local structural characteristics and the degree of spatial and sectoral integration.

3 Institutional Context: the Less Favoured Areas (LFA)

The Less Favoured Areas (LFA) is the main instrument by which the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) protects farming in physically disadvantaged areas. France introduced its own mountain allowance in 1962. The measure was harmonised at European level by Directive 75/268 of 28 April 1975 and is now co-financed 50% by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD). The integration of many municipalities into the program was facilitated by a zoning effort initiated in 1961 and 1962 in France, the year the LFA became effective.

The LFA originally pursued three goals: (i) prevent land abandonment by compensating for higher production costs in difficult terrain; (ii) prevent rural depopulation by safeguarding farm incomes and hence employment; and (iii) preserve extensive farming systems that favour landscapes and biodiversity. Over time, the emphasis has gradually shifted from merely keeping agriculture alive to promoting environmentally sustainable practices [Institute for European Environmental Policy (IEEP), 2007]. Nonetheless, the twin pillars of income stability and territorial cohesion remain explicit in successive CAP regulations.

Support is paid annually to farms located in Less Favoured Area (LFA) and is calculated per hectare of eligible area. In 2006 France was the largest single recipient, at €475 million of the €3 billion total budget of this policy. Yet because eligibility is geographically extensive (see Figure A.1 in appendix B), the average aid intensity was €110 per ha, well below Belgium's €210 or Austria's €190, suggesting a trade-off between broad coverage and per-farm impact.

In France, a farm is eligible for LFA payments only if (i) at least 80% of its utilised agricultural area lies within LFA, (ii) more than half of its income comes from farming, (iii) it maintains a minimum of three hectares of forage in the LFA together with at least five livestock units, and

(iv) its headquarters are also situated inside the zone. Regulation (EC) 1257/1999 recognises three kinds of LFA: (i) *Mountain Areas, MA*, designated under Article 18, where altitude, slope and harsh climate impose permanent cost penalties; (ii) *Simple Disadvantaged Areas, SDA*, defined in Article 19, which suffer from poor soils, low yields and demographic decline that heighten the risk of abandonment; and (iii) *Specific Handicap Areas, SHA*, set out in Article 20, where continued farming is considered essential to safeguard vulnerable ecosystems and landscapes.

Figure 1(a) illustrates the number of new municipalities classified as LFA in France each year between 1961 and 2015. France began MA zoning in 1961, designating roughly 3 500 municipalities; expansion peaked in 1976 at about 6 500 municipalities and stabilized thereafter. SDA status was added in 1976, triggering a new wave of inclusions that lasted until 1990 as policy-makers included more areas with structural disadvantages. SHA classification came later, after 1982, and grew gradually in response to environmental priorities. Since 2002, the LFA map has been broadly stable, with a slight contraction from 2012 due to tighter CAP criteria.

4 Data

We rely on a municipal-level panel dataset that merges population, agricultural, and environmental information for metropolitan France from 1962 to 1990. This period allows us to avoid the confounding effects of more recent policy changes. All datasets were harmonized to the 2023 municipal geography, yielding 34,816 units. After eliminating municipalities with zero inhabitants or jobs, excluding those classified as SDA or SHA, and retaining only municipalities designated as mountain areas—or never classified, the sample comprises 23,685 municipalities observed across five census rounds, for a total of 118,425 observations.

a) Treatment variable

LFA exposure is proxied by the official classification of a municipality as a mountain area, published by the French Ministry of Agriculture¹. This variable takes the value 1 from the first census year in which the municipality is listed as mountainous and remains so thereafter. As detailed payment amounts are unavailable for the whole period, this classification appears to be our best policy marker.

b) Outcome variables

The main dependent variables are total, salaried, and self-employed agricultural jobs measured at the workplace. Figures come from the General Population Censuses (GPC) and are available for the years 1962, 1968, 1975, 1982, and 1990. We also track employment in agri-food, industry, commerce, transport, services, construction, and public administration from the same data source. Municipal farm structure, *e.g.* number of farms, utilised agricultural area (UAA), is taken from the Agricultural Censuses (1970, 1979, 1988).

c) Control variables

¹Based on the 76/401/CEE directive.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: **Classification of municipalities as Less-Favoured Areas (LFA)**. Panel a) shows the new municipalities classified as LFA by year and by type. Panel b) shows the municipalities classified in LFA by type .

The set of control variables includes all factors likely to influence both LFA eligibility and agricultural employment.

Demographic controls (sourced from the GPC by INSEE, the National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies) measure population density, net migration, natural increase, the share of residents aged 20-64, the dependency ratio, and a synthetic education index. The latter is the first principal component of four schooling shares (no diploma, lower-secondary, upper-

secondary, tertiary), so higher values identify better-educated places. *Climatic variation* is represented by effective rainfall, total precipitation, and mean annual temperature obtained from Météo-France’s SICLIMA platform. *Biophysical characteristics* come from the European Soil Database [Panagos et al., 2012]. The texture shares (sand, loam, clay, humus) are collapsed into a single PCA index whose high scores indicate moisture-retentive, nutrient-rich clay–humus soils. Because geology evolves slowly, this soil index is treated as time-invariant. *Spatial factors* enter through a distance-weighted indicator of access to urban markets and through the population and employment densities of first-order contiguity neighbours, as job seekers often search for opportunities in nearby areas, intensifying labor market competition. The rationale for including urban proximity is that it can raise farm profitability by lowering marketing costs and broadening off-farm job options [Vandecasteele et al., 2018], whereas dense neighbours may intensify labour-market competition yet also stimulate demand for farm output [Duguet et al., 2023]. The weighted proximity index is computed as follows:

$$\text{weighted proximity}_{it} = P_{it} \times \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{1}{d_{ij}^2 + \epsilon}$$

where $\text{weighted proximity}_{it}$ denotes the weighted urban proximity for municipality i at time t . P_{it} is the population of i , d_{ij} is the distance to urban center j , and ϵ is a small constant (10^{-6}) to prevent division by zero. Urban centers are identified using INSEE’s “Aires d’Attraction des Villes” typology.

The list and sources of all variables are depicted in table B.1 in the Appendix. All covariates are lagged one census round to limit reverse causality issue. Variables that are strongly skewed, *i.e.* population density, proximity, neighbouring densities and the size of the active population (see Table 1), are log-transformed. Migration and natural balance use the inverse hyperbolic sine transformation to retain zero values and reduce the influence of outliers [Bellemare and Wichman, 2020].

Table 1 reports descriptive statistics. Across 1962–1990, the average municipality employs 72 agricultural workers (median 40); 80% are self-employed. On average, there are 15 hired jobs per municipality, but with a higher dispersion than family labour. Roughly 19,000 observations (25% of observations) ever received LFA treatment in our window. The remainder constitutes the initial control group. Pre-treatment imbalances are addressed in the identification strategy described in section 5. Figure 2 shows average wage and non-wage agricultural employment in treated vs. untreated municipalities relative to 1962. Between 1962 and 1990, salaried farm employment fell by 1.26 log-points in treated municipalities versus 1.35 in untreated ones, a relative advantage of 0.09 ($t = 12.15$, $p < 0.001$). By contrast, self-employment decreased more rapidly in treated municipalities (−0.94 log-points) than in controls (−0.74), a gap of −0.20 ($t = -35.44$, $p < 0.001$). Combined with evidence of rising average farm size and falling farm numbers, these patterns are consistent with consolidation that substitutes hired for family labour. They remain, however, purely descriptive at this point. Causal effects are estimated below using entropy balancing and staggered Difference-in-Differences.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of the variables

Variable	Obs.	Mean	SD	Min	Max	p50	p75
Total agricultural employment	118376	72.04	117.58	0.00	3986.00	40.00	80.00
Salaried agricultural employment	118376	14.77	38.96	0.00	2625.00	5.00	16.00
Self-employed agricultural employment	118376	57.27	94.54	0.00	2854.00	30.00	64.54
Agri-food employment	118376	24.51	214.06	0.00	34928.00	0.00	8.00
Employment in trade, transport, misc. services	118376	277.40	5788.28	0.00	1152521.00	16.00	60.00
Construction employment	118376	59.00	549.43	0.00	84360.00	8.00	25.00
Industrial employment	118376	182.66	1901.99	0.00	292512.00	8.00	39.00
Farm size (ha)	69978	32.86	31.73	0.00	1150.50	23.44	40.52
Utilised agricultural area (ha)	70081	2154.39	2829.85	0.00	181213.00	1419.00	2602.00
Number of farms	70004	96.30	134.49	3.00	3964.00	56.00	112.00
Population density (inh./km ²)	118424	164.86	762.76	0.34	26440.22	38.14	79.64
Effective rainfall (mm)	117975	0.98	0.67	-0.18	6.15	0.79	1.22
Average total precipitation (mm)	117975	2.37	0.78	0.00	7.40	2.21	2.71
Average temperature (°C)	117975	10.07	2.02	-1.72	16.10	10.10	11.16
Temperature amplitude (°C)	117975	6.59	1.39	0.01	11.93	6.68	7.48
Dependency ratio	118330	0.89	0.29	0.00	12.00	0.85	1.00
Working-age population (20–64)	118425	1093.62	11283.62	0.00	1639040.00	223.01	552.01
Net migration	118425	21.41	1756.91	-357870.00	82644.00	1.00	41.00
Natural balance	118425	76.34	729.26	-7157.00	118675.00	6.00	28.00
Education level	118425	0.15	1.60	-2.95	10.95	-0.14	1.03
Soil texture index	118420	-0.07	0.81	-3.99	2.63	0.11	0.47
Pop. density of neighbouring municipalities	118396	164.75	650.71	1.59	20346.05	48.90	99.83
Employment density of neighbouring municipalities	117315	0.30	0.12	0.02	6.53	0.29	0.36
Weighted urban-proximity index	118424	42041.23	331733.07	0.00	37797132.00	8429.27	20787.21

Source: Authors' calculations.

Figure 2: Average salaried and self-employed agricultural employment between treated and untreated municipalities (1962–1990), relative to 1962.

Notes: Data from 32 772 municipalities observed between 1962 and 1990. About 18 862 observations are eligible for LFA (treated) and 74 360 are not (control). The averages of salaried and self-employed employment are calculated over the entire period.

5 Specification and identification Strategy

a) Direct Effects of the LFA

Adopting the dynamic specification of [Hornbeck and Keskin \[2015\]](#), we estimate the programme's impact on salaried and self-employed farm labour. In order to express the effects relative to the pre-programme period (1962), we difference outcomes over time as follows:

$$Y_{ct} - Y_{c,1962} = \alpha_0 + \beta_t \cdot LFA_c + \theta_1 X_{ct} + \alpha_t + \alpha_c + \alpha_{ct} + \varepsilon_{ct}. \quad (1)$$

where Y_{ct} is the outcome for municipality c in year t (salaried, self-employed or total employment); LFA_c is a time-invariant binary variable equal to 1 if municipality c receives LFA support; X_{ct} is the vector of controls described above; α_c , α_t , and α_{ct} denote municipality fixed effects, year fixed effects, and municipality–year fixed effects, respectively; ε_{ct} is the idiosyncratic error term. We cluster standard errors at the municipality level to account for heteroskedasticity and serial correlation within municipalities.

The parameters β_t capture the policy’s trajectory and are identified under two key assumptions. First, in the absence of policy, LFA and non-LFA municipalities would have followed a similar evolution over time (common-trend assumption). Comparability before the NCHA is important to ensure this assumption. Second, assignment is exogenous to the outcomes of interest. This assumption can be challenging to maintain because mountain municipalities were selected precisely because employment was fragile.

To approximate random assignment, we use the *entropy balancing* approach [Hainmueller, 2012]. Pre-treatment covariate moments of the untreated group are re-weighted to match those of the treated municipalities and the resulting weights enter equation (1), yielding an Average Treatment effect on the Treated (ATT)(see Appendix E). The main advantages of this approach are that it is non-parametric, achieves exact balance on chosen moments, and avoids multicollinearity by making the re-weighted covariates orthogonal to the LFA_c assignment [Neuenkirch and Neumeier, 2016]. Finally, because our study period does not include a large pre-treatment window, entropy balancing is particularly well-suited.

However, endogeneity may persist through time-varying unobservables that simultaneously affect the treatment and agricultural employment. We therefore lag all controls by one census, retain climate-invariant soil texture, and include municipality and year dummies to absorb fixed shocks. Nevertheless, since LFA activity in one municipality affects employment in its neighbours, ordinary DiD estimates will confound direct and indirect effects. We address this below.

b) Total Effect, Sectoral Multipliers, and Geographic Spillovers

We extend this strategy to estimate the *total* effect of the LFA. Our aim is to capture both (i) sectoral multiplier effects and (ii) geographic spillover effects of the LFA on agricultural employment. Indeed, the LFA may influence employment not only where it is paid but also in neighboring areas, so the Stable Unit Treatment Value Assumption (SUTVA) that underlies most causal designs is unlikely to hold. Naïve Difference-in-Differences confound own-municipality gains with neighbour-induced changes, biasing total-effect estimates [Roth et al., 2023, Butts, 2021]. Sectoral multipliers may also be at work. To distinguish between these channels we follow an additive-spillover² framework Butts [2021]:

²An additive spillover means that every treated unit within a given radius contributes separately and cumulatively to the total effect on a treated or untreated unit [Butts, 2021].

$$Y_{cts} - Y_{c,1962} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 LFA_c + \sum_{j \in \text{Dist}} \delta_j IE_{ct,j} + \theta_1 X_{ct} + \alpha_c + \alpha_t + \varepsilon_{ct}, \quad (2)$$

where Y_{cts} is employment in sector s (agriculture, industry, agri-food, etc.) for municipality c at time t , capturing the effects of LFA on other sectors. Geographic spillovers are captured by $IE_{ct,j}$, the share of c 's neighbours within distance band j that are treated. We use three concentric rings, $\text{Dist} = (0, 15], (15, 30], (30, 45]$ km-to represent distance bands in kilometers. The exposure index for band j is:

$$\text{IE}_{ct} = \frac{\sum_j w_{cj} LFA_{jt}}{\sum_j w_{cj}}$$

where w_{cj} is an entry of the spatial-weights matrix (1 if c and j are contiguous, 0 otherwise)³. In order to capture exposure intensity, equation (2) is modified by replacing the LFA dummy with the interaction between the treatment and the exposure index, $LFA_{ct} \times \text{IE}_{ct}$. The coefficient β_1 then gives the total LFA effect on treated municipalities, while the coefficients $\delta_j = (1 - LFA_{it})$ are the average spillovers on non-LFA municipalities in each distance band.

Following Butts [2021], we estimate total and spillover effects in two stages, each time using entropy balancing. First, β_1 is identified by contrasting LFA municipalities that *are* exposed (at least one treated neighbour) with non-LFA municipalities that *are not* exposed (no treated neighbour). Because spillovers fade sharply beyond the first border, this “exposed versus unexposed” comparison is valid so long as no meaningful externalities extend beyond immediately contiguous municipalities. Empirical checks confirm that effects vanish after 45 km, our outer ring. Second, for treated units we compare exposed LFA municipalities with municipalities but unexposed ones, while for controls we compare exposed and unexposed non-LFA municipalities. This yields separate δ_j for each ring. Reweighting is repeated for every distance band to keep covariate moments aligned (see Table D.1 in the Appendix).

Overall, this specification captures both sectoral multipliers and geographic spillovers. By jointly estimating β_1 and the δ_j , we can decompose the program’s impact: the shifts in employment within recipient municipalities, in agriculture located in neighboring municipalities, and in other activities further away.

6 Results

We employ entropy balancing to reweight untreated municipalities so that their covariate moments exactly match those of LFA recipients. Section D presents the results of this procedure and shows that, once weighted, all pre-treatment mean differences become statistically insignificant, confirming the validity of the counterfactual.

³Figures (B.1) and (B.2) in Appendix A display the distribution of this index for contiguity and distance bands.

6.1 Direct and Dynamic Effects of the LFA on Agricultural Employment

We estimate equation (1) with the entropy-balancing weights. Full estimation results are in Table D.1. All coefficients are expressed as percentage deviations from the 1962 baseline.⁴ Table 2 summarizes the results where columns [1], [2] and [3] provide the direct impacts on, respectively, *total* agricultural employment; *salaried* agricultural employment and *self-employed* agricultural employment.

Panel A of Table 2 reveals a pronounced compositional shift. On average across 1962-1990, LFA eligibility raises *salaried* farm jobs by about 10% (0.0939 log-points), yet cuts self-employed labour by 0.200 log-points, or 18%.⁵ Because family labour supplies more than four-fifths of the farm workforce (Table 1), the rise in paid employment cannot compensate for its loss and total agricultural employment ends up 15% lower than in the non-LFA municipalities. These estimates indicate the substitution of hired for family labour predicted when subsidies promote mechanisation and scale enlargement [Gallardo and Sauer, 2018, Alexiadis et al., 2013].

Panel B clarifies when this reallocation occurred. At the first post-baseline census (1968) treated municipalities lagged behind controls for both labour types: salaried jobs are 34% lower and self-employment 24% lower. Between 1969 and 1976, however, most mountain municipalities began receiving LFA transfers. By 1975 the salaried gap had closed (a statistically insignificant +1%), while the self-employment deficit narrowed only slightly to 18%. The turning-point came in 1982: salaried employment was then 34% *above* the counterfactual, whereas self-employment remained 17% below. The positive wage-labour lead persisted in 1990 (+21%), even as family labour continued to retreat (-22%). Hence the LFA did not produce an immediate jump in paid jobs; rather, its effects unfolded gradually, consistent with the time needed for farms to reorganise production and labour contracts.

Total agricultural employment (Panel B, column [1]) follows the same pattern as self-employed labour. Although total employment fell significantly as early as 1968, the decline is milder thereafter (1975, 1982, 1990) because the opposite movements of salaried and self-employed labour partly offset each other. As self-employed workers account for around 85 % of the agricultural workforce (Table 1); the rise in salaried employment is therefore insufficient to compensate for the sharp fall in self-employed jobs.

Figures 3(a), 3(b) and 3(c) depict the estimated trends in total, salaried and self-employed agricultural employment relative to non-LFA municipalities and to 1962. They reveal a marked drop in total and self-employed employment between 1962 and 1990, especially from 1962 to 1968, followed by a modest rebound. Figure 3(b) also highlights a fall in salaried employment up to 1968 and an increase thereafter, implying a positive dynamic effect on salaried jobs from 1968 onward and a persistent negative effect on self-employed and total agricultural employment.

Our findings highlight mixed results regarding the distribution of labor on farms as non-salaried employment (family labor) and salaried employment on farms have not evolved uniformly: non-

⁴The log-coefficient γ is converted as $(e^\gamma - 1) \times 100$.

⁵see Table F.1 in Appendix F for full results.

Table 2: Dynamic effects of the LFA on agricultural employment (deviation from 1962)

	(1) log(Total employment)	(2) log(Salaried employment)	(3) log(Self employment)
Panel A: Direct impact			
LFA (Yes/No)	-0.165*** (-6.64)	0.0939* (1.82)	-0.200*** (-6.32)
Panel B: Dynamic effects			
LFA ₁₉₆₂	0	0	0
LFA ₁₉₆₈	-0.225*** (-3.79)	-0.340*** (-3.69)	-0.238*** (-3.20)
LFA ₁₉₇₅	-0.151*** (-3.49)	0.0069 (0.07)	-0.181*** (-3.01)
LFA ₁₉₈₂	-0.115** (-2.13)	0.343*** (4.29)	-0.167** (-2.50)
LFA ₁₉₉₀	-0.181*** (-3.29)	0.210*** (3.84)	-0.219*** (-3.42)
Municipalities / Obs.	23,583 / 93,174	23,583 / 93,174	23,583 / 93,174
R ²	0.208	0.204	0.184
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes
Municipality FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes

Notes: Weighted least squares estimates using entropy-balancing weights. The table reports only the treatment coefficients (variables of interest); for detailed results on other control variables, see Table F.1 and Table F.2. *t*-statistics clustered at the municipality level are reported in parentheses. ***, **, and * indicate significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

salaried employment is declining, while salaried employment is increasing. This leads to an overall negative effect, as illustrated by data showing a persistent decrease in non-salaried agricultural employment in municipalities receiving the LFA payments, alongside a rise in salaried employment. Although the negative impact of the LFA payments on total agricultural employment may seem counter-intuitive in light of the program’s initial objectives, this result nevertheless aligns with the theoretical literature, which emphasizes that the share of agricultural employment tends to decline as economic growth progresses and public subsidies increase [Anderson et al., 2013, Christiaensen et al., 2021] and that subsidies encourage farmers to adopt less labor-intensive and more mechanized forms of agriculture, leading to a reduced need for unskilled labor [Edan et al., 2009, Gallardo and Sauer, 2018, Alexiadis et al., 2013]. Thus, despite an overall negative effect on agricultural employment, the LFA appears to have met some of its specific aims (*i.e.* maintaining farming activity in disadvantaged areas and countering rural depopulation) by reducing reliance on unskilled family labour in favour of more formal employment arrangements.

6.2 Total Effect and Geographic Spillovers on Agricultural Employment

Table 3 summarises the spillover estimates from equation (2) with s being agricultural employment. Only the coefficients of interest, β_1 and δ_j , are reported.

For salaried employment, Panel A shows that once neighbour⁶ spillovers are accounted for, the LFA boosts salaried employment in recipient municipalities by about 21% (0.194–0.193 log-points, columns [1]–[2]), hereby double the 10% effect obtained when spillovers are ignored

⁶We use successively the rook and the queen contiguity definition to neighbourhood.

(a) Dynamic effects of the LFA on total agricultural employment

(b) Dynamic effects of the LFA on salaried employment

(c) Dynamic effects of the LFA on self-employment

Figure 3: **Dynamics effects of LFA** : Figures plot estimated differences between LFA and non-LFA municipalities for each year, relative to 1962, based on equation (1). Dashed lines show 95% confidence intervals.

(Table 2). Columns [3]–[4] compare treated municipalities that are exposed to other treated neighbours with treated but unexposed ones; the extra gain is significant only within 0–15 km, implying sharply localised positive externalities. Columns [5]–[6] restrict the sample to non-LFA municipalities: those bordering a treated neighbour also enjoy a significant 0–15 km bonus, which vanishes beyond that radius. Hence, the programme raises salaried employment both directly and through short-range spillovers to any contiguous municipality.

For self-employment, Panel B indicates that, once spillovers are accounted for, the LFA still depresses family labour in beneficiary municipalities, but the loss shrinks to roughly 7% (columns [1]–[2]) compared with the 18% found earlier. Proximity to other treated municipalities (columns [3]–[4]) offsets part of that decline, again only inside the 15 km ring. Untreated neighbours (columns [5]–[6]) exhibit no significant spillover, confirming that household labour remains tied to the recipient farm’s own adjustment.

Summarizing, for both labour types, all significant spatial externalities disappear beyond 15 km, showing that LFA benefits and costs disperse over very short distances. This spatial pattern matches agglomeration theory, which stresses that knowledge, labour and market linkages attenuate quickly with distance [Duranton and Puga, 2004, Giroud et al., 2024].

Table 3: Estimated geographic spillover effects of the LFA on agricultural employment

Panel A: Deviation of log salaried agricultural employment relative to 1962						
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
LFA × IE (rook contiguity)	0.194*** (0.009)					
LFA × IE (queen contiguity)		0.193*** (0.009)	0.0635 (0.536)		0.249*** (0.002)	
IE (Neighbours 0–15 km)				0.362** (0.023)		0.353* (0.060)
Observations	89,993	98,996	18,853	18,853	74,321	74,321
Adjusted R^2	0.129	0.129	0.196	0.198	0.131	0.130
Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Municipality FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Panel B: Deviation of log self-employed agricultural employment relative to 1962						
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
LFA × IE (rook contiguity)	-0.0740** (0.018)					
LFA × IE (queen contiguity)		-0.0719** (0.018)	0.216*** (0.000)		0.0245 (0.664)	
IE (Neighbours 0–15 km)				0.222* (0.057)		-0.0280 (0.835)
Observations	89,993	89,960	18,853	18,853	74,321	74,321
Adjusted R^2	0.150	0.150	0.171	0.173	0.196	0.196
Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Municipality FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Notes: *** (**) (*) denote significance at the 1, 5, and 10 percent level. Standard errors in parentheses, clustered by municipality and year. IE = exposure index. All regressions include entropy-balancing weights and the urban-proximity index in baseline controls. Study period: 1962–1990.

6.3 Sectoral and Geographic Spillover Effects of the LFA

Table 4 estimates equation (2) where s related to non-farm sectors: agri-food, trade-transport-services, construction, and industry.

Panel A shows that relative to 1962, LFA status raises employment in trade-transport-services by 29% and in industry by 10%. Coefficients for agri-food and construction are positive but not significant, indicating that the allowance mainly stimulates commercial and industrial activities linked to farm demand.

Panel B (rows 3 and 4) presents the spillovers estimated for untreated neighbors. Municipalities that do not receive the LFA yet share a border with a treated municipality record significant gains in trade-transport-services and in industry. Effects for agri-food and construction are positive but imprecisely estimated. Disaggregating by distance shows that, again, these benefits are confined to the first 15 km. For LFA recipients (rows 7 and 8), additional exposure to neighbouring recipients boosts agri-food, construction and industry employment within the 0–15 km ring, but effects weaken sharply beyond that radius, again confirming the high localisation of externalities.

The LFA therefore exerts two distinct channels of influence outside agriculture: a direct boost to trade-related and industrial jobs within beneficiary municipalities, and short-range spillovers to adjacent areas—treated or not—particularly in sectors most tied to farm input and output flows. The rapid decay of coefficients across distance bands underscores the pivotal role of geographic proximity in transmitting these multipliers.

Table 4: Geographic and sectoral spillover effects of the LFA

	<i>Agri-food</i> [1]	<i>Trade, Transport and Misc. Services</i> [2]	<i>Construction</i> [3]	<i>Industry</i> [4]
PANEL A: Total effect on the treated				
(1) Total effect on the treated (ATT)	0.00742 (0.814)	0.253*** (0.000)	0.0303 (0.392)	0.100*** (0.002)
(2) Observations	89 960	89 960	89 960	89 960
PANEL B: Spillover effects on the untreated				
(3) IE (queen contiguity)	0.0795 (0.251)	0.297*** (0.000)	0.104 (0.135)	0.178** (0.020)
(4.1) IE (neighbours 0–15 km)	0.235 (0.188)	0.0838 (0.556)	0.0874 (0.466)	-0.0321 (0.816)
(4.2) IE (neighbours 15–30 km)	-0.0354 (0.860)	0.0573 (0.655)	0.205 (0.338)	0.436 (0.143)
(4.3) IE (neighbours 30–45 km)	-0.196 (0.160)	0.304 (0.102)	-0.123 (0.415)	-0.192 (0.234)
(6) Observations	74 321	74 321	74 321	74 321
PANEL C: Spillover effects on the treated				
(7) IE (queen contiguity)	0.119** (0.023)	0.0128 (0.819)	0.195*** (0.001)	0.116* (0.081)
(8.1) IE (neighbours 0–15 km)	0.0437 (0.565)	-0.0112 (0.854)	0.0690 (0.713)	0.0588 (0.687)
(8.2) IE (neighbours 15–30 km)	0.0134 (0.896)	0.0816 (0.553)	0.153 (0.305)	0.287 (0.106)
(8.3) IE (neighbours 30–45 km)	0.127 (0.241)	0.122 (0.297)	0.110 (0.466)	0.00731 (0.935)
(9) Observations	18 853	18 853	18 853	18 853

Notes: *** (**) (*) indicate statistical significance at the 1 Standard errors (in parentheses) are clustered at the municipality level for rows 1, 2, 4, 7 and at the municipality-year level for regressions using distance rings (rows 3 and 5); see Giroud et al. [2024]. In addition to the covariates, we include neighbouring population density and neighbouring employment density.

We performed a series of robustness checks by changing the sample, adding extra controls and applying alternative estimation methods. All our results, displayed in Appendix G, confirm our main results.

We also performed an heterogeneity analysis (the results are displayed in Appendix H). They show that the LFA’s employment effects are not uniform but vary according on farm structure and location. Gains in salaried employment arise mainly in municipalities with small-to-medium holdings, many farms and limited UAA, and are amplified when the municipality lies close to an urban center, benefiting from higher market access and labour pooling. By contrast, the positive wage effect fades on very large or land-abundant farms. The contraction of self-employed labour is widespread but deepest where average farm size is already high; it persists regardless of distance to cities, confirming that family work retreats whenever land consolidation proceeds. Overall, the allowance succeeds in generating paid jobs only up to structural and spatial thresholds; beyond them, it mainly accelerates the displacement of family labour without creating

new salaried positions.

6.4 Transmission Mechanisms

Our baseline estimates reveal that LFA municipalities substitute paid for family labour. To uncover the channels, we focus on three structural variables: the number of farms (Ex), utilised agricultural area (UAA), and average farm size (UAA/Ex), all highlighted in work linking subsidies to land use and consolidation [Ito et al., 2019, Gallic and Marcus, 2019, Takayama et al., 2020, 2021].

Table 5 presents the estimates of fixed-effects regressions of salaried and self-employed jobs on each candidate channel, adding the usual covariates plus municipality, department and year dummies. For salaried labour (cols. [1]–[3]) both UAA and average farm size enter positively and significantly, while Ex is insignificant. For self-employed labour (cols. [4]–[6]) UAA and Ex are positive, but farm size is negative. In other words, expanding land and enlarging farm sizes favour paid jobs, corresponding to more skilled labour, yet diminish family work, whereas simply adding farms supports family labour.

Equation (1) is re-estimated with each channel as the dependent variable and LFA as the dependent variable, using entropy-balancing weights. Table 6 shows that the LFA expands UAA, raises average farm size and reduces farm numbers. Thus, the LFA speeds up land consolidation and specialisation, exactly the configuration that step 1 linked to rising salaried and falling family employment.

To quantify how much of the LFA effect runs through each channel, we adopt the causal-mediation framework of Nguyen et al. [2022], decomposing the Average Treatment Effect (ATE) into a Natural Direct Effect (NDE) and a Natural Indirect Effect (NIE). Results are in Table 7. For salaried labour, the indirect path through average farm size explains 22% of the total gain (column [1]); through farm numbers, only 16% (columns [3]–[4]); through UAA, a striking 83% (columns [5]–[6]). Because UAA and farm size are collinear, their shares are not additive, but the ranking in the mediation is clear: land expansion is the dominant mediator for job creation. For self-employed labour, the negative LFA effect is almost entirely mediated by land expansion and farm enlargement: the NIE equals 102% of the total for farm size and 115% for UAA, with a modest 11% contribution from fewer farms. A positive NDE partially offsets these large negative NIEs, yielding the -7% net loss reported earlier. LFA encourages farmers to enlarge holdings and bring idle plots into production, lowering average costs but increasing capital requirements. Larger, more mechanised units hire skilled workers and dispense with unpaid family help, a pattern documented elsewhere [Edan et al., 2009, Gallardo and Sauer, 2018]. Consequently, salaried employment rises while self-employment shrinks.

Table 5: Transmission channels and salaried vs. self-employed agricultural employment: Panel fixed-effects OLS

	Salaried agricultural employment			Self-employed agricultural employment		
	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]
$\log(\text{Number of farms})$	0.0120 (0.60)			0.493*** (25.85)		
$\log(\text{Utilised agricultural area})$		0.0749*** (4.77)			0.231*** (12.89)	
$\log(\text{Average farm size})$			0.0631*** (3.73)			-0.0931*** (-5.38)
Observations	90,962	91,128	90,933	90,962	91,128	90,933
adj. R^2	0.394	0.395	0.395	0.331	0.324	0.322
Covariates	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Municipality FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Département FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Notes: *** (**) (*) denote significance at the 1 (5) (10) % level. Robust standard errors, clustered at the municipality level, in parentheses.

Table 6: Impact of the LFA on the transmission channels

	(1)	(2)	(3)
	$\log(\text{Number of farms})$	$\log(\text{Utilised agricultural area})$	$\log(\text{Average farm size})$
LFA (treated = 1)	-0.114*** (-22.98)	0.0251*** (3.69)	0.142*** (29.37)
Municipalities / Observations	23,248 / 91,195	23,246 / 91,360	23,244 / 91,171
R^2	0.719	0.675	0.631
Covariates	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES
Region FE	YES	YES	YES
Département FE	YES	YES	

Notes: *** (**) (*) denote significance at the 1 (5) (10)

Table 7: Mediation analysis

	Mediator: Average farm size		Mediator: Number of farms		Mediator: Utilised agricultural area	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	Salaried employment	Self-employed employment	Salaried employment	Self-employed employment	Salaried employment	Self-employed employment
Indirect effect (NIE)	0.030*** (0.006)	-0.108*** (0.006)	0.026*** (0.003)	-0.012*** (0.001)	0.143*** (0.005)	-0.121*** (0.005)
Direct effect (NDE)	0.106*** (0.014)	0.002 (0.011)	0.140*** (0.013)	-0.090*** (0.011)	0.028** (0.013)	0.012 (0.010)
Total effect (TE)	0.137*** (0.013)	-0.106*** (0.011)	0.166*** (0.013)	-0.102*** (0.011)	0.171*** (0.013)	-0.109*** (0.011)
Proportion explained	0.221*** (0.047)	1.020*** (0.103)	0.157*** (0.020)	0.114** (0.016)	0.834*** (0.066)	1.115*** (0.103)
Observations	91,834	91,834	91,858	91,858	92,027	92,027

Notes: *** (**) (*) denote significance at the 1 (5) (10)

7 Discussion of the results

Our results indicate that the LFA encourages hired agricultural labour while reducing family self-employment, mainly through farm consolidation (larger UAA, higher average farm size, fewer holdings). Subsidies may induce small farms to merge or sell land, leading to a decline in the number of family units whereas enlarged farms recruit more workers. This substitution is consistent with Kaditi [2013] for Greece and aligns with work showing that the CAP’s employment effect depends on job category and subsidy type [Dupraz and Latruffe, 2015, Bojnec and Fertó, 2022]. Also, LFA impacts vary with average farm size (AFS), number of farms (NOF), utilised agricultural area (UAA) and distance to cities. We find a positive, significant rise in salaried employment, yet a persistent drop in family labour, where farms are small or medium, holdings are few, UAA is moderate and urban proximity is high. In large farms the impact weakens or disappears, likely because capital-intensive holdings invest transfers in mechanisation rather than jobs [Edan et al., 2009, Gallardo and Sauer, 2018]. Smaller units, lacking such capital, convert support into labour. Hence, the LFA robustly suppresses self-employment while boosting formal jobs where structural constraints are tight. By narrowing wage gaps between farm and non-farm work, LFA payments also reduce the incentive for worker to exit agriculture—a classic “income effect”.

The FP7 CAP-IRE report (2011)⁷ corroborates these patterns. It predicts that, with current CAP rules, 20% of EU farms will close within a decade, concentrating land in fewer, larger holdings; without subsidies, an extra 30%—mostly in disadvantaged areas—would exit, sharply cutting labour. This supports our finding that subsidies restructure the sector by sustaining hired labour and limiting reliance on family workers. Similarly, Olper et al. [2014] estimate that CAP support reduced out-migration from farming by 24–28% across EU regions. Overall, although the LFA reduces farm numbers, its promotion of larger, viable holdings and expanded UAA aligns with its original goals: sustain agricultural activity in hard-to-farm regions, curb land abandonment and provide stable earnings that can slow rural exodus.

Beyond direct effects, the LFA generates sizeable spillovers for neighbouring municipalities and multipliers for non-farm sectors. Including spatial lags shows that the positive effect on hired farm labour strengthens, while the negative impact on family labour attenuates. Treated municipalities show significantly higher employment in trade, transport, services and industry than untreated ones. Untreated neighbours likewise gain—especially in industry and commerce/transport/services—though benefits fade with distance. Treated localities that are themselves surrounded by other treated areas also see gains in the agri-food chain, construction and industry, but these vanish beyond 15 km, an elasticity remarkably close to the “local multiplier” estimated by Moretti [2010]. Such distance decay underscores the importance of proximity, mirroring multiplier effects documented by Blomquist and Nordin [2017], Hornbeck and Keskin [2015] and illustrate the short reach of agglomeration economies.

The underlying mechanisms can be interpreted through agglomeration-economy theory, which distinguishes three channels [Duranton and Puga, 2004]: matching (larger local labour pools im-

⁷<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/216672/reporting>

prove worker–firm matches), sharing (firms share infrastructure, suppliers and skilled workers) and learning (knowledge diffuses faster at close range). Indeed, proximity lets non-beneficiary municipalities adopt innovations from subsidised neighbours. LFA funds may finance new technologies or management practices that spread informally, raising productivity and hired labour demand nearby [Giroud et al., 2024]. Our results show that positive spillovers to hired labour, and negative ones to self-employment, are confined to immediate neighbours and disappear beyond 15 km. Also, treated areas benefit from better input supply and cheaper logistics, stimulating wholesale, retail and related services; agro-food firms and industrial firms in adjacent towns also benefit. Although we lack direct flow data, Table 4 reveals higher employment in trade, transport, services and industry once spatial effects are included, again concentrated in close-range rings.

Two institutional features could foster these local spillovers. On the one hand, pooling expensive machinery, CUMA (“Coopératives d’Utilisation de Matériel Agricole”) reduce investment costs; LFA funds can expand these cooperatives, and their benefits spill into neighbouring municipalities through shared equipment and know-how. On the other hand, even without formal CUMA, subsidies lower upfront costs and encourage farmers—especially smallholders—to share tractors, harvesters, etc. Such flexible sharing spreads gains to nearby farms and boosts local employment.

8 Conclusion and policy implications

This paper assessed the long-run impact of the Less Favoured Areas program (LFA) on French agriculture from 1962 to 1990, teasing out direct labour effects and the indirect, and possibly unexpected, spatial spillovers that place-based transfers can unleash. We combined entropy balancing with a staggered differences-in-differences design to correct endogeneity, ensure parallel trends, and accommodate the scheme’s phased introduction.

Results show that the LFA permanently increases salaried employment while cutting self employment. Including neighbouring municipalities magnifies the hiring gains and softens the family-labour decline, indicating that consolidation, fewer holdings, larger average size, more cultivated land—drives a substitution of wage labour for family work. Positive spillovers also reach non-farm sectors such as trade, services, industry, and agri-food processing, underlining the program’s capacity to fuel broader rural growth. Spatial diffusion, however, decays beyond roughly 15km.

Our paper highlights that the LFA, though effective in fostering salaried employment and stimulating some non-agricultural sectors, also generated unintended structural changes. Such patterns illustrate how policies conceived with narrowly defined goals can trigger broader territorial dynamics, sometimes reinforcing, sometimes diverting from their initial objectives. For policy-makers, this implies that design and evaluation should systematically integrate potential indirect and spatial effects, ensuring that interventions remain aligned with evolving economic, demographic, and environmental contexts.

Moreover, our results suggest three policy reflections for the present CAP programming period. First, because support favours larger, current targeting seems misaligned with the CAP 2023-2027 objective of bolstering small, resilient farms; recalibrated aid could channel more resources toward independent structures pursuing agro-ecological practices. Second, the evidence that benefits spill across municipal borders and value chains highlights the need for an integrated territorial approach in which transfers like the LFA should be designed and bundled with transport, digital infrastructure, vocational training and local innovation hubs to reinforce multipliers. Third, rural heterogeneity argues against one-size-fits-all governance; differentiating payments by structural and geographic context, and evaluating them with tools that trace inter-municipal linkages and sectoral interactions, would enhance both efficiency and equity. Such adjustments are becoming urgent as climate mitigation, generational renewal and the defence of rural employment converge on rural policy agendas.

Our work could be extended by (i) adding municipal-level subsidy amounts in order to identify intensity effects on treated areas; (ii) recovering pre-1962 data to longer-run dynamics explore longer-run dynamics; (iii) documenting inter-sector and inter-territorial flows to map spillover channel more precisely. Granular financial and trade data would further enable spatial general-equilibrium analysis of place-based agricultural policy.

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Online Appendix: Additional Tables and Figures

A Mountain areas delimitation

Figure A.1: [Map of Mountain Areas](#)

Delimitation of mountain areas and exposure of cities

B Definitions of the variables

Table B.1: Variable descriptions

Variable name	Variable description	Source and period	Link (URL)
1. Variable of interest			
LFA (Yes/No)	Classification status: Mountain Area, Ordinary Disadvantaged Area or Specific Handicap Area	<i>Data.gov (1962–1990)</i>	https://www.data.gov.fr/fr/datasets/communes-de-montagne-30383014/
LFA exposure index	Share of neighbouring municipalities that are treated (queen or rook contiguity)	Authors' calculation	–
2. Dependent variables			
Number of farms	Economic units engaged in agricultural production with independent management	<i>Agreste – Agricultural Census, 1970–2020</i>	https://agreste.agriculture.gouv.fr/agreste-web/disaron!/searchurl/searchUuid/search/
Utilised agricultural area (UAA)	Arable land, permanent crops, permanent grassland, vegetable/flower areas, etc.	<i>Agreste – Agricultural Census, 1970–2020</i>	https://agreste.agriculture.gouv.fr/agreste-web/disaron!/searchurl/searchUuid/search/
Average farm size	Ratio of UAA to the number of farms	<i>Agreste – Agricultural Census, 1970–2020</i>	https://agreste.agriculture.gouv.fr/agreste-web/disaron!/searchurl/searchUuid/search/
Total agricultural employment	Jobs located in agriculture, forestry and fishing	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/information/2880845
Salaried agricultural employment	... (salaried positions only)	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/information/2880845
Self-employed agricultural employment	... (self-employed positions only)	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/information/2880845
Industrial employment	Jobs in manufacturing, extractive industry, etc.	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/information/2880845
Employment in trade, transport and miscellaneous services	Jobs in wholesale/retail trade, transport and other services	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/information/2880845
Construction employment	Jobs in building and civil engineering (BTP)	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/information/2880845
Agro-food employment	Jobs in food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/information/2880845
2.1 Demographic characteristics			
Population density	Inhabitants per km ²	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/3698339
Population aged 0–19	Number of inhabitants aged 0–19	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/3698339
Population aged 20–64	Number of inhabitants aged 20–64	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/3698339
Population aged 64+	Number of inhabitants aged 64 and over	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/3698339
Total population	Total number of inhabitants	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/3698339
Dependency ratio	$\frac{\text{Pop (0–19)} + \text{Pop (64+)}}{\text{Pop (20–64)}}$	Authors' calculation	–
Net migration	In-migrants minus out-migrants	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/3698340
Natural balance	Births minus deaths over an intercensal period	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/3698341
No diploma / \leq lower-secondary	Persons with at most the BEPC or no diploma	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/3698342
Upper-secondary – Baccalauréat	Persons who completed upper-secondary education (BAC)	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/3698343
Tertiary education	Persons with higher-education qualifications	<i>INSEE/Quetelet – Population Census, 1962–2020</i>	https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/3698344
2.2 Physical soil characteristics			
Sandy soil	Mostly sand; porous, low water retention	<i>Joint Research Centre [Panagos et al., 2012]</i>	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2011.07.003
Clay soil	Mostly clay; heavy and compact	<i>Joint Research Centre [Panagos et al., 2012]</i>	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2011.07.003
Loamy soil	Mostly silt; medium porosity	<i>Joint Research Centre [Panagos et al., 2012]</i>	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2011.07.003
Humic soil	Rich in organic matter; good drainage	<i>Joint Research Centre [Panagos et al., 2012]</i>	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2011.07.003
2.3 Geographic characteristics			
Urban-proximity index	Total municipal population divided by distance-weighted sums to nearby cities	Authors' calculation	–
Neighbouring-municipality density	Distance-weighted population density of contiguous neighbours	Authors' calculation	–
Neighbouring-employment density	Distance-weighted employment of contiguous neighbours	Authors' calculation	–

All variables are defined at municipal level. RA = Agricultural Census. INSEE = National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies. Population-census data for 1962–1990 are accessed via Quetelet (<https://data.progedo.fr/>).

C Natural Handicap Compensation Allowance (LFA) exposure index

Figure B.1: LFA exposure index based on contiguity

Figure B.2: LFA exposure index by distance bands

D Covariate Balance

The first step in entropy balancing matches the means of all covariates, using one-year-lagged municipal variables to minimise potential reverse causality. Panel A of Table D.1 compares unweighted sample means for every regression covariate. Observations in which a municipality receives the LFA form the treatment group (column [1]); observations without LFA support constitute the control group (column [2]). Column [3] shows mean differences and the corresponding p -values for the null of no difference. Treated and untreated periods differ significantly on every

pre-treatment characteristic except the dependency ratio. Treated municipalities experience heavier precipitation, more episodes of effective rainfall and higher neighbouring-employment density; by contrast, they have lower population density, lower average temperatures, weaker migration and natural balances, lower education levels, a poorer soil-texture index and less urban proximity. These differences highlight the need for an appropriate control group to obtain unbiased treatment-effect estimates.

Panel B of Table D.1 reports covariate means for the treatment group (column [1]) and for the synthetic control group produced by entropy balancing (column [4]). Column [5] lists the mean differences and their p -values. None of the covariate gaps remain statistically significant—all p -values exceed the conventional 0.10 threshold. In short, weighting eliminates all pre-treatment imbalances, achieving perfect covariate balance and confirming the effectiveness of entropy balancing. The resulting weighted control group therefore provides a credible counterfactual based on observables, so that any residual outcome differences can be attributed to the treatment alone.

Table D.1: Descriptive statistics: covariate balance before and after entropy balancing

	[1]	[2]	[3] = [1] - [2]	
Panel A: Before balancing				
<i>Variable</i>	LFA	No LFA	Difference	p -value
$\log(\text{Population density})_{t-1}$	2.977	4.023	-1.046	0.000
Soil-texture index	-0.392	0.012	-0.404	0.000
$\log(\text{Weighted urban proximity})_{t-1}$	8.499	8.850	-0.351	0.000
$\log(\text{Neighbour pop. density})_{t-1}$	3.327	4.251	-0.925	0.000
$\log(\text{Neighbour emp. density})_{t-1}$	0.289	0.263	0.026	0.000
Effective rainfall $_{t-1}$	1.753	0.815	0.939	0.000
Mean precipitation $_{t-1}$	3.234	2.175	1.058	0.000
Mean temperature $_{t-1}$	8.616	10.164	-1.549	0.000
Dependency ratio $_{t-1}$	0.917	0.918	-0.002	0.475
$\log(\text{Active population})_{t-1}$	5.001	5.673	-0.672	0.000
$\text{asinh}(\text{Net migration})_{t-1}$	-0.411	0.281	-0.692	0.000
$\text{asinh}(\text{Natural balance})_{t-1}$	-0.715	2.022	-2.737	0.000
$\log(\text{Education index})_{t-1}$	-0.473	0.141	-0.614	0.000
Observations	23,285	74360		
	[1]	[4]	[5] = [1] - [4]	
Panel B: After balancing				
<i>Variable</i>	LFA	Synthetic control	Difference	p -value
$\log(\text{Population density})_{t-1}$	2.998	3.004	-0.006	0.401
Soil-texture index	-0.389	-0.388	-0.001	0.896
$\log(\text{Weighted urban proximity})_{t-1}$	8.513	8.514	-0.001	0.964
$\log(\text{Neighbour pop. density})_{t-1}$	3.349	3.353	-0.004	0.464
$\log(\text{Neighbour emp. density})_{t-1}$	0.289	0.289	0.000	0.875
Effective rainfall $_{t-1}$	1.760	1.757	0.003	0.571
Mean precipitation $_{t-1}$	3.239	3.236	0.004	0.541
Mean temperature $_{t-1}$	8.580	8.587	-0.007	0.661
Dependency ratio $_{t-1}$	0.916	0.915	0.000	0.928
$\log(\text{Active population})_{t-1}$	5.039	5.043	-0.004	0.549
$\text{asinh}(\text{Net migration})_{t-1}$	-0.384	-0.372	-0.012	0.645
$\text{asinh}(\text{Natural balance})_{t-1}$	-0.683	-0.667	-0.016	0.438
$\log(\text{Education index})_{t-1}$	-0.434	-0.429	-0.005	0.531
Observations	18,862	74,360		
Total weights	18,862	18,862		

Notes: Panel A reports raw means; Panel B reports weighted means after entropy balancing. Column labels correspond to treatment, unweighted control, and synthetic (weighted) control groups. p -values test equality of means.

E Identification strategy

Our target parameter is the Average Treatment Effect on the Treated (ATT), defined as

$$ATT(\chi) = \mathbb{E}[Y_i(1) \mid LFA_i = 1] - \mathbb{E}[Y_i(0) \mid LFA_i = 1]. \quad (3)$$

Here, $LFA_i = 1$ is an indicator equal to 1 when municipality i receives the LFA transfer (i.e. is classified as a mountain area) in period t , and 0 otherwise. $\mathbb{E}[Y_i(1) \mid LFA_i = 1]$ is the observed outcome—total agricultural employment, salaried agricultural employment or self-employed agricultural employment—after treatment. $\mathbb{E}[Y_i(0) \mid LFA_i = 1]$ is the counterfactual outcome that the same municipality would have registered had it not received the LFA. Because a given municipality cannot be simultaneously treated and untreated, the counterfactual is unobservable. If treatment were randomly assigned, the average outcome for untreated units, $\mathbb{E}[Y_i(0) \mid LFA_i = 0]$, would be a valid proxy. As mountain classification is likely endogenous, a naïve difference would yield a biased estimate.

To overcome this difficulty we mimic random assignment by comparing LFA municipalities with non-LFA municipalities that share similar *pre-treatment* characteristics related (i) to the probability of classification and (ii) to agricultural employment. The identification assumption is that, conditional on these observables, treated and control municipalities were indistinguishable before treatment, so that any post-treatment gap can be attributed to the policy. Formally, we rewrite (3) as

$$ATT(\chi) = \mathbb{E}[Y_i(1) \mid LFA_i = 1, X = \chi] - \mathbb{E}[Y_i(0) \mid LFA_i = 0, X = \chi]. \quad (4)$$

where $X = \chi$ is a vector of pre-treatment covariates that jointly influence both the likelihood of receiving the LFA and—potentially—agricultural employment. Conditional on X , assignment to the LFA (mountain classification) is assumed to be independent of the outcome.

F Additional results

Table F.1: Main results: Average effect, deviation relative to 1962

	(1) log(total agricultural employment)	(2) log(salaried)	(3) log(self-employed)
Mountain area (Yes/No)	-0.165*** (0.025)	0.094* (0.052)	-0.200*** (0.032)
log(population density _{t-1})	-0.055*** (0.018)	0.126*** (0.029)	-0.088*** (0.023)
Effective rainfall _{t-1} (mm)	0.146* (0.081)	0.952*** (0.138)	0.154 (0.099)
Average total precipitation _{t-1} (mm)	-0.191** (0.079)	-0.895*** (0.129)	-0.187* (0.099)
Mean temperature _{t-1} (°C)	0.059*** (0.009)	-0.021 (0.015)	0.073*** (0.012)
Dependency ratio _{t-1}	-0.042 (0.028)	-0.115*** (0.036)	-0.033 (0.031)
log(pop. 20-64 _{t-1})	0.066*** (0.023)	-0.185*** (0.039)	0.072** (0.028)
log(net migration _{t-1})	-0.013*** (0.003)	0.020*** (0.005)	-0.017*** (0.003)
log(natural balance _{t-1})	0.017*** (0.003)	0.020*** (0.006)	0.017*** (0.004)
Soil-texture index _{t-1}	-0.016 (0.012)	-0.040* (0.021)	-0.002 (0.015)
Education level _{t-1}	-0.006 (0.023)	0.011 (0.038)	-0.015 (0.029)
log(urban-proximity index _{t-1})	0.007 (0.005)	-0.025*** (0.008)	0.018** (0.008)
log(contiguity density _{t-1})	-0.072*** (0.016)	-0.059 (0.037)	-0.074*** (0.021)
log(total population density _{t-1})	0.763*** (0.155)	-0.691*** (0.244)	0.629*** (0.181)
Municipalities / Observations	23 583 / 93 174	23 583 / 93 174	23 583 / 93 174
R ²	0.208	0.195	0.184
Year fixed effects	YES	YES	YES
Municipality fixed effects	YES	YES	YES

Notes: The table shows the average treatment effect (LFA beneficiary municipalities) estimated with weighted OLS (Entropy Balancing). Only coefficients for the treatment and covariates are displayed. ***, **, * denote significance at the 1 *t*-statistics clustered at the municipality level are in parentheses. The reference year is 1962 (coefficients equal zero).

Table F.2: Main results: Dynamic effects, deviation relative to 1962

	(1) log(total agricultural employment)	(2) log(salaried)	(3) log(self-employed)
LFA ₁₉₆₂	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)
LFA ₁₉₆₈	-0.225*** (0.059)	-0.340*** (0.092)	-0.238*** (0.074)
LFA ₁₉₇₅	-0.151*** (0.043)	0.007 (0.093)	-0.181*** (0.060)
LFA ₁₉₈₂	-0.115** (0.054)	0.343*** (0.080)	-0.167** (0.067)
LFA ₁₉₉₀	-0.181*** (0.055)	0.210*** (0.055)	-0.219*** (0.064)
log(population density _{t-1})	-0.054*** (0.019)	0.138*** (0.028)	-0.087*** (0.024)
Effective rainfall _{t-1} (mm)	0.160* (0.085)	0.935*** (0.127)	0.166 (0.107)
Total precipitation _{t-1} (mm)	-0.205** (0.081)	-0.906*** (0.122)	-0.199* (0.104)
Mean temperature _{t-1} (°C)	0.063*** (0.009)	-0.006 (0.014)	0.076*** (0.013)
Dependency ratio _{t-1}	-0.044 (0.027)	-0.134*** (0.034)	-0.034 (0.029)
log(pop. 20-64 _{t-1})	0.065*** (0.022)	-0.194*** (0.034)	0.071** (0.028)
log(net migration _{t-1})	-0.013*** (0.002)	0.022*** (0.005)	-0.016*** (0.003)
log(natural balance _{t-1})	0.018*** (0.003)	0.025*** (0.006)	0.017*** (0.004)
Soil-texture index _{t-1}	-0.016 (0.013)	-0.022 (0.020)	-0.002 (0.017)
Education level _{t-1}	-0.005 (0.023)	0.011 (0.034)	-0.014 (0.029)
log(urban-proximity index _{t-1})	0.007 (0.004)	-0.025*** (0.008)	0.018** (0.008)
log(contiguity density _{t-1})	-0.073*** (0.016)	-0.062* (0.034)	-0.074*** (0.021)
log(total population density _{t-1})	0.748*** (0.155)	-0.746*** (0.241)	0.617*** (0.182)
Municipalities / Observations	23 583 / 93 174	23 583 / 93 174	23 583 / 93 174
R ²	0.208	0.204	0.184
Year fixed effects	YES	YES	YES
Municipality fixed effects	YES	YES	YES

Notes: The table reports the average treatment effect (LFA beneficiary municipalities) and dynamic effects, estimated with weighted OLS (Entropy Balancing). Only coefficients for the treatment and covariates are displayed. ***, **, * denote significance at the 1 t-statistics clustered at the municipality level are in parentheses. The reference year is 1962 (coefficients equal zero).

G Robustness

G.1 Robustness Checks

Alternative sample

We use an alternative sample to ensure that our results are not driven by a specific subgroup within the dataset. First, we consider an expanded sample that includes all disadvantaged areas in the treatment group—that is, municipalities classified as mountain areas (MA), as well as those designated as simply disadvantaged (SDA) or areas with specific handicaps (SHA). Panel A of Table G.1 presents the results obtained from estimating Equation 1 using the entropy balancing method with this new sample. The findings confirm the robustness of our baseline conclusions: a positive and significant effect on salaried agricultural employment (column 2, Panel A), as well as a negative and significant effect on non-salaried agricultural employment and total agricultural employment (columns 1 and 3 of Panel B, respectively). Finally, we observe a persistent decline in non-salaried agricultural employment in municipalities benefiting from the LFA payments, relative to non-beneficiary municipalities, alongside a rise in salaried employment. This indicates a substitution effect between salaried and non-salaried employment.

Sensitivity to outliers

We also examine the sensitivity of our results to outliers.⁸ We exclude these outliers to obtain a new sample. Specifically, outliers are defined as observations with standardized residuals (in absolute value) greater than 1.96 and a Cook’s distance exceeding the empirical threshold of $4/NT$, where NT corresponds to the number of observations in a balanced panel. This approach assumes a 95% confidence level that non-outlier observations are part of the true data. The observations considered outliers are thus removed from the sample. The results are presented in Panel B of Table G.1, using the same estimation method as before, with standard errors clustered at the municipal level. The findings are also consistent with our baseline conclusions: the LFA payments have a positive and significant effect on salaried agricultural employment (column 2, Panel B), and a negative and significant effect on non-salaried and total agricultural employment (columns 1 and 3 of Panel B, respectively) in beneficiary municipalities compared to non-beneficiaries. Moreover, these results reveal a persistent decline in family labor (non-salaried employment) in LFA beneficiary municipalities, relative to the 1962 baseline and to non-beneficiary municipalities. This trend is accompanied by an increase in salaried agricultural employment in these same beneficiary municipalities since 1975. These findings reinforce our initial conclusions.

Alternative methods

To verify that the findings do not depend on the estimation technique, we apply two staggered-adoption DID approaches: (i) the Callaway-and-Sant’Anna DID estimator [Callaway and Sant’Anna, 2021] and (ii) the staggered Entropy-DID. Because both methods require an untreated baseline at $t = 0$ (1962), we drop municipalities already treated in 1962, thereby creating

⁸This strategy is used by Acemoglu et al. [2019].

Table G.1: Robustness to alternative sample and outliers

	(1)	(2)	(3)
	log(agricultural employment)	log(salaried)	log(self-employed)
PANEL A: Including all disadvantaged areas			
LFA (Yes/No)	-0.141*** (-7.55)	0.0761*** (2.68)	-0.171*** (-7.51)
LFA1962	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)
LFA1968	-0.0933*** (-3.88)	-0.177** (-2.41)	-0.100*** (-3.79)
LFA1975	-0.0957*** (-3.49)	-0.0621 (-1.39)	-0.0934*** (-3.21)
LFA1982	-0.139*** (-5.78)	0.187*** (4.16)	-0.188*** (-6.09)
LFA1990	-0.168*** (-5.90)	0.0918*** (3.33)	-0.197*** (-6.12)
Municipalities / Observations	32 644 / 129 048	32 644 / 129 048	32 644 / 129 048
R^2	0.149	0.124	0.135
Covariates	YES	YES	YES
Municipality FE	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES
PANEL B: Excluding outliers			
LFA (Yes/No)	-0.107*** (-6.57)	0.0889* (1.83)	-0.143*** (-6.46)
LFA1962	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)
LFA1968	-0.168*** (-3.53)	-0.340*** (-3.82)	-0.191*** (-3.06)
LFA1975	-0.0631* (-1.86)	0.109 (1.46)	-0.0977* (-1.81)
LFA1982	-0.0965* (-1.77)	0.295*** (3.79)	-0.162** (-2.44)
LFA1990	-0.108*** (-5.74)	0.170*** (3.28)	-0.124*** (-5.89)
Municipalities / Observations	23 484 / 86 513	23 484 / 86 513	23 484 / 86 513
R^2	0.336	0.280	0.286
Covariates	YES	YES	YES
Municipality FE	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES

Notes: The table tests robustness to the alternative sample (Panel A) and to outliers (Panel B) using weighted OLS (Entropy-balancing weights). Only the coefficients of interest are reported. ***, **, * indicate significance at the 1 t -statistics clustered at the municipality level are in parentheses. The reference year is 1962 (coefficients equal zero).

a genuine pre-treatment window for the common-trend test. Results should be interpreted with caution, since not all treated municipalities remain in the sample. If the common-trend assumption is violated, the Callaway–Sant’Anna estimates are biased [Cefalu et al., 2020]. Combining DID with entropy weights mitigates that risk by balancing covariates and aligning pre-treatment trends, yielding reliable estimates even when raw trends are non-parallel.

Columns [1]–[3] of Table G.2 present the Callaway–Sant’Anna DID results; columns [4]–[6] show the Entropy-DID estimates. All models pass the pre-trend test, reinforcing their credibility. Columns [3] and [6] indicate a positive and significant LFA effect on salaried employment—average impacts of 0.170 and 0.364 log-points, respectively—and an early rise from 1975, peaking in 1982 (see Fig. G.1). By contrast, columns [1] and [2] show negative but insignificant effects on total and self-employed employment, whereas the Entropy-DID in columns [4] and [5] yields negative and significant impacts for both. From 1975 onward, total and self-employed employment decline, while salaried employment grows (Fig. G.1), confirming substitution. The weaker significance on self-employed jobs likely reflects the exclusion of early-treated municipalities, which form a sizeable share of the original sample (Fig. 1).

To restore those municipalities, we introduce a *placebo* year (1954), assuming no change in covariates between 1954 and 1962. Columns [7]–[9] re-estimate the DID with the full sample. The positive, significant effect on salaried employment persists, while effects on total and self-employed employment remain negative but insignificant, leaving our main conclusions unchanged.

Table G.2: **Robustness: alternative methods**

	DID (Callaway–Sant’Anna)			Entropy-DID			Placebo year 1954		
	[1] AET	[2] AENS	[3] AES	[4] AET	[5] AENS	[6] AES	[7] AET	[8] AENS	[9] AES
ATT	-0.00524 (-0.10)	-0.0309 (-0.60)	0.170** (2.59)	-0.330** (-1.97)	-0.382** (-2.15)	0.364* (1.69)	-0.0312 (-0.80)	-0.0520 (-1.14)	0.131** (2.05)
Dynamic effects									
T ₁₉₇₅	0.0569	0.0382	0.217*	-0.0616	-0.0262	0.124	0.0186	0.00603	0.158**
T ₁₉₈₂	-0.0197	-0.0531	0.164*	-0.570**	-0.734**	0.639*	-0.0387	-0.0650	0.142**
T ₁₉₉₀	-0.165*	-0.188*	0.0266	-0.417	-0.403	0.274	-0.178**	-0.208**	0.00343
Pre-trend test (<i>p</i> -value)	2.7558 (0.431)	2.8713 (0.412)	5.6361 (0.131)	1.7419 (0.628)	0.7825 (0.854)	6.6964 (0.822)	3.3730 (0.338)	3.0434 (0.385)	4.4002 (0.221)
Observations	78 700	78 700	78 700	78 700	78 700	78 700	99 341	99 341	99 341
Covariates	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Notes: Robustness checks using staggered DID estimators. Columns (1)–(3) and (7)–(9) use the Callaway–Sant’Anna DID; columns (4)–(6) combine entropy balancing with DID. ***, **, * denote significance at the 1 AET = total agricultural employment; AENS = self-employed agricultural employment; AES = salaried agricultural employment.

Figure G.1: Robustness: dynamic effects

Additional control variables

This section assesses the robustness of our findings by testing the baseline model's sensitivity to extra controls. A key concern is the omission of potential determinants of agricultural employment that are correlated with our treatment—here, the LFA. If such determinants are ignored they are absorbed by the error term, which is assumed to be uncorrelated with the regressors; violating that assumption creates an endogeneity risk.

To limit this bias we augment the baseline equation (1) with two additional controls: temperature amplitude and the presence of geographical indications.

Temperature amplitude, defined as the gap between the daily maximum and minimum temperature, is crucial for agricultural activity at the municipal level and thus for employment. *Geographical indications* (GI) link the quality, reputation or characteristics of a product to a specific place; they help differentiate, protect and enhance agricultural and food products. By securing market outlets and raising producers' and processors' income, GIs stimulate rural employment. We approximate this with a dummy that equals 1 from the year a product obtains controlled designation of origin (CDO)/protected designation of origin (PDO) and protected geographical indications (PGI), and 0 otherwise.

Labelling dates are taken from: (i) *eAmbrosia*, the EU's official GI portal; (ii) *Eur-Lex*, for the relevant EU regulations; (iii) *INAO*, the French database of CDO, PGI and "Label Rouge" products; and (iv) *Legifrance*, for French decrees and ministerial orders. Including these controls helps isolate the specific impact of the LFA on agricultural employment.

Table G.3 reports the estimates after adding the extra controls. Columns [1]–[3] include the GI

dummy; columns [4]–[6] add temperature amplitude; columns [7]–[9] include both. In every case, the results corroborate our baseline conclusions, confirming the robustness of our estimates.

Table G.3: Robustness: additional control variables

	CDO/PDO/PGI label			Temperature amplitude			Label + amplitude		
	[1] AET	[2] AES	[3] AENS	[4] AET	[5] AES	[6] AENS	[7] AET	[8] AES	[9] AENS
LFA	-0.166*** (0.0252)	0.0934* (0.0507)	-0.201*** (0.0321)	-0.164*** (0.0246)	0.0948* (0.0511)	-0.200*** (0.0314)	-0.166*** (0.0250)	0.0941* (0.0502)	-0.201*** (0.0320)
LFA ₁₉₆₂	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LFA ₁₉₆₈	-0.208***	-0.337***	-0.222***	-0.227***	-0.345***	-0.238***	-0.210***	-0.341***	-0.223***
LFA ₁₉₇₅	-0.164***	0.00496	-0.192***	-0.148***	0.0162	-0.180***	-0.160***	0.0131	-0.191***
LFA ₁₉₈₂	-0.122**	0.342***	-0.174***	-0.110**	0.355***	-0.167***	-0.117**	0.353***	-0.173***
LFA ₁₉₉₀	-0.180***	0.210***	-0.218***	-0.185***	0.199***	-0.219***	-0.186***	0.199***	-0.220***
<i>N</i>	93 174	93 174	93 174	93 174	93 174	93 174	93 174	93 174	93 174
adj. <i>R</i> ²	0.210	0.195	0.185	0.208	0.196	0.183	0.210	0.196	0.185
Covariates	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Municipality FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Notes: The table tests robustness by adding extra controls. Columns (1)–(3) include only the GI dummy; columns (4)–(6) include only temperature amplitude; columns (7)–(9) include both. ***, **, * denote significance at the 1 *t*-statistics clustered at the municipal level appear in parentheses. AET = total agricultural employment; AENS = self-employed agricultural employment; AES = salaried agricultural employment.

H Heterogeneity Analysis

Our baseline estimates indicate that the LFA raises salaried agricultural employment but lowers self-employment. We now ask whether these effects differ by (i) average farm size (AFS), (ii) utilised agricultural area (UAA), (iii) number of farms (NF) and (iv) distance to the nearest urban centre. For each dimension we split the sample at the median—“low” versus “high” groups, following [Apeti and Edoh \[2023\]](#)—and re-estimate the treatment effects separately for salaried and self-employed labour. All regressions keep the full set of covariates plus municipality and year fixed effects.

Average farm size. When we divide communes by AFS, Panel A of Table [H.1](#) shows that the LFA’s positive impact on salaried jobs is larger, though not statistically significant, in areas with very large farms, and positive as well as significant in areas with small-to-medium farms. The fall in self-employment is steeper in the large-farm group, implying that salaried positions are created mostly on smaller holdings, whereas family labour declines across the board, especially on the largest farms.

Number of farms. Panel B compares communes with few farms (high concentration) to those with many. The wage-labour boost is strongest where NF is low, while the negative effect on self-employment is weaker where NF is high. This mirrors national trends: the INSEE counts a drop from 1.6 million farms in 1970 to roughly 390 000 in 2020.⁹

Utilised agricultural area. Splitting by UAA, we find that the LFA stimulates salaried employment only where land area is small or moderate; it sharply reduces self-employment in both groups. In communes with extensive UAA, the wage effect disappears, but the family-labour decline remains.

Urban proximity. Finally, we distinguish communes close to a city from those that are remote. Prior research suggests that peri-urban farms benefit from better prices, easier market access and wider use of modern inputs, increasing demand for hired labour while displacing family labour [[Vandecasteele et al., 2018](#)]. Panel D confirms that urban proximity amplifies the LFA’s positive effect on salaried jobs—perhaps because marketing services and labour exchanges are more readily available—yet the programme still cuts self-employment regardless of distance.

Overall, the LFA generates salaried jobs and displaces family workers through all three structural channels, but the wage gains fade once farms become very large, land is abundant, or market access is limited, suggesting a threshold beyond which additional support no longer translates into formal employment growth.

⁹<https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/7728861?sommaire=7728903>

Table H.1: **Treatment heterogeneity**

	Salaried employment		Self-employed employment	
PANEL A: Average farm size (AFS)				
	[Low AFS]	[High AFS]	[Low AFS]	[High AFS]
LFA (Yes/No)	0.115** (2.31)	0.143 (1.55)	-0.202*** (-6.70)	-0.206*** (-2.72)
Observations	49 294	43 880	49 294	43 880
R^2	0.237	0.139	0.235	0.144
Covariates	YES	YES	YES	YES
Municipality FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
PANEL B: Number of farms (NF)				
	[Low NF]	[High NF]	[Low NF]	[High NF]
LFA (Yes/No)	0.379*** (4.71)	-0.0471 (-1.18)	-0.245*** (-3.97)	-0.135*** (-5.35)
Observations	47 628	45 546	47 628	45 546
R^2	0.124	0.273	0.130	0.306
Covariates	YES	YES	YES	YES
Municipality FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
PANEL C: Utilised agricultural area (UAA)				
	[Low UAA]	[High UAA]	[Low UAA]	[High UAA]
LFA (Yes/No)	0.159** (2.44)	0.00346 (0.08)	-0.262*** (-6.66)	-0.102*** (-2.67)
Observations	47 298	45 876	47 298	45 876
R^2	0.208	0.148	0.189	0.237
Covariates	YES	YES	YES	YES
Municipality FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
PANEL D: Weighted urban-proximity index (IPPU)				
	[Low IPPU]	[High IPPU]	[Low IPPU]	[High IPPU]
LFA (Yes/No)	0.0844 (1.24)	0.107** (2.10)	-0.230*** (-4.87)	-0.152*** (-3.74)
Observations	44 690	48 484	44 690	48 484
R^2	0.234	0.150	0.182	0.200
Covariates	YES	YES	YES	YES
Municipality FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES

Notes: *** (**) (*) indicate significance at the 1 Robust standard errors (in parentheses) are clustered at the municipality level.